

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS ON SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN'S LIFESTYLE AND HEALTH BEHAVIOR IN A SELECTED SCHOOL IN SAN JUAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Most children who were ardent users of social media sites were of school-age (6 to 12 years old) and considered to be in their formative years. With that, this paper aims to explore the strength of social media's influence on health behaviors and the lifestyle of school-aged children in a selected school in San Juan, with sleep, nutrition/diet, activity, and mental health being the main factors focused on. This quantitative research utilized the stratified random sampling method to collect data. It has been noted that among sleep, activity, nutrition/diet, and mental health, activity has been impacted by the use of social media (weighted mean of 2.52), and it did not obstruct the children from having a fulfilling social life outside of their homes; the rest have been less impacted — Impact to sleep (weighted mean of 2.22), Impact to Nutrition/diet (weighted mean of 2.37), and Impact to Mental health (weighted mean of 2.49). In terms of significance, only the impacts of activity and nutrition/diet had no correlation to each other while the rest of the factors were correlated. Therefore, school-aged children's lifestyles and behaviors were not affected by social media platforms, however, appropriate advice and education should still be provided to support the child's optimal overall growth and development and to prevent any dangers that could be harmful to their health. Furthermore, future researchers are encouraged to engage in this kind of studies so as to further elucidate on how too much exposure to social media could alter one's health.

Keywords: *Social Media, Lifestyle, Behavior, and School-age Children*

INTRODUCTION

Children experience different effects in using social media with the positive effects outweighing the negative one (Bizieff, 2021). It has shown to enhance communication, engagement, and in improving learning experience (Chassiakos et al, 2016). However, the longer-term impacts of social media on growing children's brains have been found to be more detrimental with violence and aggression, sexual content, low body image and self-esteem, physical health, and poor academic achievement to name a few (Bizieff, 2021).

Social media is used significantly more by younger people than older people. The utilization of these platforms became rampant in the pediatric population especially by school-aged children; social media platforms namely Facebook, YouTube, and Tiktok are commonly utilized by this age group. In this modern age, the convenience of social media and the internet has been widely incorporated in daily lives. Since the brains of school-aged children are still developing, they are more receptive to their environment including data coming from these social media sites. This eventually influences brain activity including their behavioral patterns and responses as they get used to these social media's dopamine-like effects on their brain. Prioritizing social media use over healthy practices like getting enough sleep, exercising, and eating right could lead to compromising a child's overall development and growth. Filipino pediatricians acknowledge the negative effects of social media use, however, these are not often discussed during consultations. Therefore, enhanced media training in residency programs is necessary through addressing obstacles and social media education during anticipatory guidance to improve counseling. (Orduna et al., 2019).

This study aims to determine if social media platforms have an influence on the health behavior and lifestyle of school-aged children in a selected school in San Juan City. The results of this study, titled "The Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-Aged Children's Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan City," will be shared with the selected school with the aim of informing the administration and faculty of the impacts of social media to their elementary student's behaviors and lifestyle. With the rampant use of social media by school-aged children, knowing the degree of strength social media has on these children may serve as a stepping stone for better behavioral and lifestyle management with the help of their guardians and enhanced nursing care, especially that of nurses whose line of work directly affects children.

Research Questions

Nowadays, social media usage is significantly high by younger people than older people. The utilization of these platforms became rampant in the pediatric population especially by school-aged children. In this modern age, the convenience of social media and the internet has been widely incorporated in daily lives. Thus, this research aims to determine the Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-age Children's Lifestyle and Health Behavior. This also sought to find the answers to these questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex of the parent/guardian
 - 1.2 Sex of the child
 - 1.3 Age of the child
 - 1.4 Grade level of the child

2. What are the Children Social Media Platforms involvement in the following:
 - 2.1 Own gadget
 - 2.2 Type of gadget being used
 - 2.3 Social Media account
 - 2.4 Access to social media platform
 - 2.5 Type/s of social media platforms

3. What is the frequency of the Children's usage of Social Media Platforms on a daily basis in terms of:
 - 3.1 Time
 - 3.2 Hours

4. What exposure to social media platforms affect the lifestyle of those school age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of:
 - 4.1 Impact to sleep
 - 4.2 Impact to activity

5. What effect does daily use of social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Tiktok on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of:
 - 5.1 Nutrition/Diet
 - 5.2 Mental Health

6. Is there a significant relationship between the impact of social media platforms on school-age children's lifestyle and health behavior in a selected school in San Juan City?

METHODOLOGY

The Quantitative research method was used to investigate this study. Quantitative approach collects quantifiable information from a larger number of participants to be used for statistical analysis. This method was delivered through survey and questionnaire. This research was based on the analysis and findings of gathered data in this area. Therefore, a descriptive research methodology was used to gain accurate and factual profiling.

The population were parents of School-age Children in a selected School in San Juan, both male and female. The used sampling method in this study was stratified random sampling due to the respondents being divided into a smaller scope which were based on a specific age-range and grade level which was 6 to 12 years old, grades 1 to 6 children.

The respondents who answered our google form surveys were the parents or guardians of the school-age children in San Juan City. The said respondents should meet the criteria in order for their answers to be valid and accepted. First, parents/ guardians should be 18 - 59 years old. Should be able to read and understand English. Should be able to give informed consent and must be living with the child. However, those who have serious physical and mental disabilities were excluded.

The researchers constructed a 24-item questionnaire entitled "The Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-Aged Children's Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan". It contained one cover letter with a consent form and guidelines explaining to the respondents the importance of their response to the study. The questionnaire was designed with a scale format, with a rating of 1 being no impact and a rating of 4 with high impact. It was further validated by a pediatrician and then distributed once approval had been granted. To test the reliability of the study, Cronbach alpha was utilized and had a value of 0.76 which is interpreted as acceptable. The questionnaire divided in profile of the respondents, information on the types of social media platforms the school-age children were engaged into, exposure to social media platforms which affected the lifestyle those school-aged children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to sleep and activity and effect of daily use of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to nutrition/diet and mental health. It was transferred to google forms to have easy access to the respondents. It used an arbitrary scale to help interpret and determine the impact

of social media platforms on school-age children’s lifestyle and health behavior in a selected school in San Juan City.

Arbitrary Scale used to interpret the gathered data:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretations	Adjectival Description
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	With High Impact
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree	With Impact
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree	With Less Impact
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree	With No Impact

RESULTS

A formal permission coursed through a letter was secured to the selected school in San Juan City. The researchers then constructed a 24-item questionnaire checklist entitled “The Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-Aged Children’s Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan”, and had it validated by an expert. Upon distribution, all of the participants were informed of the purpose, expectations and research methodology, and they were asked to sign consent forms explaining that the survey was strictly confidential and voluntary. The questionnaire was disseminated via Google Form. The data gathered were then collected, tallied and tabulated.

Table 1: Profile of the Parents / Guardian in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	24
Female	38	76
Total	50	100%

Table 1 shows that most of the guardians/parents of the school-aged children who answered the questionnaire were 38 females (76%) followed by 12 males (24%).

Table 2: Profile of the Child in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	58
Female	21	42
Total	50	100%

Table 2 shows the sex of school-age children; respondents were 39 boys (58%) and 21 girls (42%).

Table 3: Profile of the Child in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
12	11	22
11	4	8
10	7	14
9	2	4
8	9	18
6	17	34
Total	50	100%

Table 3 indicates the Age of School-age Children; respondents include 17 children under 6 years old (34%), 9 children under 8 years old (18%), 2 children under 9 years old (4%), 7 children under 10 years old (14%), 4 children under 11 years old (8%), and 11 children under 12 years old (22%).

Table 4: Profile of the Child in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
6	13	26
5	4	8
4	6	12
3	8	16
2	3	6
1	16	32
Total	50	100%

Table 4 shows the Grade level of School-aged Children; respondents included 16 children from Grade 1 (32%), 3 children were in Grade 2 (6%), 8 children were in Grade 3 (16%), 6 children were in Grade 4 (12%), 4 children were in Grade 5 (8%) and 13 children were in Grade 6 (26%).

Table 5: School-age Children own a gadget/s

Children	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	44	88
No	6	12
Total	50	100%

As shown in table 5, 88% of the school-age children owned a gadget/s and 12% did not own any gadget/s.

Table 6: School-age Children Type of Gadget/s

Gadgets	Frequency	Percentage
Mobile Phone	26	52
Tablet/Ipad	19	38
Laptop	2.5	5
Laptop/tablet	2.5	5
Total	50	100%

Table 6 described the types of gadgets used by the school-age children to access social media platforms. Majority which was 52% respondents used Mobile Phones to access social media. Followed by 38% respondents who used Tablet/Ipad, 5% respondents used Laptop and 5% respondents used both Laptop/Tablet and Cellphone/Ipad.

Table 7: School-aged Children have Social Media Account

Children	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	32	64
No	18	36
Total	50	100%

Table 7 shows that about 64% of the parents/guardians answered that their children had social media accounts and 36% had answered that their children did not have any social media accounts.

Table 8: School-age Children have access to Social Media Account

Children	Frequency	Percentage
Have access	43	86
Do not have access	7	14
Total	50	100%

Table 8 shows 86% percent responded that their children do not have their own gadget/s but still had access to any social media platforms. While 14% responded that they did not have neither their own gadget nor access to any social media platforms.

Table 9: School-age Children Type Social Media Platforms

Gadgets	Frequency	Percentage
Youtube	35	43
Tiktok	24	29
Facebook	23	28
Total	82	100%

Table 9 indicates that *YouTube* was found to be the most frequent social media platform among the school-aged children based on their parents/guardians (70%), followed by *Tiktok* (48%), and *Facebook* (46%) respectively. This shows that the simultaneous oral-based interactions made possible by platforms like YouTube and Tiktok were more prevalent on the social media sites frequented by school-age children.

Table 10: School-age Children Daily usage of Social Media Platforms in terms of times

Times	Frequency	Percentage
more than 5	15	30
4-5	6	12
3-4	16	32
1-2	13	26
Total	50	100%

Table 10 shows how related to the daily frequency usage of social media platforms. Almost 32% of the respondents acknowledged that they used these platforms at least 3 to 4 times daily. In particular, 30% of them reported that they used it more than 5 times daily, 26% of them used it 1 to 2 times daily and 12% used it 4 to 5 times daily.

Table 11: School-aged Children Daily usage of Social Media Platforms in terms of Hours

Hours	Frequency	Percentage
more than 5	10	20
4-5	6	12
3-4	16	32
1-2	18	36
Total	50	100%

Table 11 shows the hours' children spent in a day in using social media platforms. Around 36% responded that their children used social media in a day for about 1 to 2 hours. While 32% answered that their usage of social media lasted for about 3 to 4 hours. 12% of them

voted for 4 to 5 hours. Lastly, 20% had more than 5 hours of usage of social media in a day.

Table 12: Exposure to Social Media Platforms Affect the Lifestyle those School aged Children in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Sleep

Impact to Sleep	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My child has had a hard time sleeping after consistently using social media before bedtime.	2.46	Agree
2. Social media use before bedtime helps my child relax better.	2.20	Disagree
3. My child prefers to stay up all night to use social media than to rest.	2.24	Disagree
4. My child uses social media to help him/her sleep.	2.18	Disagree
5. My child's energy levels are low the morning after using social media.	2.14	Disagree
6. My child wakes up refreshed when he/she uses social media before bedtime.	2.10	Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.22	Disagree (With Less Impact)
Standard Deviation	.12712	

Table 12 shows the exposure to social media platforms affect the lifestyle of those school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Sleep. The highest computed weighted mean of 2.46 was found in the statement number 1, "My child has had a hard time sleeping after consistently using social media before bedtime" with verbal interpretation. This implied that the parents agreed that their child had a hard time sleeping after using social media like Facebook before going to bed.

Based on the finding of Arora et al. (2013) using cell phones, playing video games, watching TV, or browsing the internet all shorten or worsen sleep. While it could be noticed that the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.10 was found in statement number 6, "My child wakes up refreshed when he/she uses social media before bedtime". This meant that parents disagreed with this statement. This implies that even if their child used social media before going to bed, parents still observed their child woke up refreshed and rested.

The over-all computed weighted mean was 2.22 with verbal interpretation of disagree. This meant that the exposure to social media platforms affected the lifestyle of those school-aged children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Impact to sleep had **Less Impact**.

Table 13: Exposure to Social Media Platforms Affect the Lifestyle those School-aged Children in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Activity

Impact to Activity	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My child still has the time to go outside and play with friends.	3.22	Agree
2. My child prefers to stay at home rather than engaging in social activities.	2.06	Disagree
3. Social media platforms help my child to perform exercises (watching videos about exercise)	2.30	Disagree
4. Utilization of social media platforms persuades my child to become lazy.	2.40	Disagree
5. He/She still has the time to engage in exercising activities.	2.66	Agree
6. My child prefers to play/use gadgets rather than playing outside.	2.50	Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.52	Agree (With Impact)
Standard Deviation	.39606	

Table 13 shows exposure to social media platforms affected the lifestyle of those school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Activity. The highest computed weighted mean of 3.22 was found in the statement number 1, “My child still has time to go outside and play with friends” with verbal interpretation, agree. This meant that even when kids were into social media platforms they still found time to mingle with their friends as observed by the parents especially during the pandemic when they were not allowed to go out with their friends.

While the lowest computed mean of 2.06 was found in statement number 2, “My child prefers to stay at home rather than engaging in social activities. This validated the

response of the parents that their children still would like to go out with their friend instead of just staying at home.

The over-all computed weighted mean was 2.52 with verbal interpretation, agree. This meant that exposure to social media platforms affected the lifestyle of those school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to activity ***With Impact***.

Promoting smart media use, technology could become a beneficial aspect of childhood. On public television, preschoolers could learn the alphabet, grade schoolers could use educational apps and games, and teenagers could conduct online research (Ben-Joseph, 2022).

Table 14: Effect of Daily use of Social Media Platforms on the Health Behavior of School-aged Children in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Nutrition/Diet

Impact to Nutrition /Diet	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My child focuses on eating without the distraction of social media platforms.	2.76	Agree
2. Social media influences my child to eat unhealthy foods.	2.38	Disagree
3. Social media positively affects my child's food choices.	2.30	Disagree
4. My child refuses to eat while watching social media platforms.	2.26	Disagree
5. Social media influences my child to eat healthy foods.	2.32	Disagree
6. My child loses his/her appetite due to usage of social media platforms.	2.22	Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.37	Disagree (With Less Impact)
Standard Deviation	.19704	

Table 14 shows the effect of daily use of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-aged children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Nutrition/Diet. The highest computed weighted mean of 2.76 was found in the statement number 1, "My child focuses on eating without the distraction of social media platforms"

verbally interpreted, agree. This implied that guidance of the parents was an important factor to discipline their child when it comes to eating time.

Parents sitting together with their children at the dining table was a positive implication. The lowest computed weighted mean of 2.22 was found in the statement number 6, "My child loses his/her appetite due to usage of social media platforms" with verbal interpretation disagree. This validated the highest computed weighted mean. This implied the discipline/rules had to be communicated in terms of breakfast/lunch/dinner. This would be a great help so nutrition/diet would not be affected.

The overall weighted mean of 2.37 with verbal interpretation disagree This implied that there was **Less Impact** on the daily use of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Nutrition/Diet.

Stamatiou et al. (2021), study on social media constructs opportunities and challenges for public health promotion. Social media users habitually come up with nutrition and body-related information shared by health and non-health professionals. In this study, social media were found to be the preferred nutrition information source; Instagram, YouTube and Facebook were said to be the most used platforms. Healthcare professionals like Dieticians' social media accounts were said to be the most trusted source. However, user's dietary options appeared affected by social media; in terms of their feeling about food consumption and seeing delicious images of food yet less nutritious food.

Table 15 shows the effect of daily use of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to mental health. The highest computed weighted mean of 3.12 was found in the statement number 3, "Social Media platforms have helped my child in his/her schoolworks" with verbal interpretation, agree. This implied that social media helped students in finding resources in their schoolworks. This meant social media had positive uses in the studies of children. There are available applications that can be helpful.

While the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.08 was found in the statement number 2, "My child prefers to stay at home rather than socializing with other kids outside our house" with verbal interpretation, disagree. This meant kids still wanted to play outside with their friends.

Table 15: Effect of Daily use of Social Media Platforms on the Health Behavior of School-aged Children in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Mental Health

Impact to Mental Health	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Social media has helped in boosting my child's confidence.	2.64	Agree
2. My child prefers to stay at home rather than socializing with other kids outside our house.	2.08	Disagree
3. Social media platforms have helped my child in his/her schoolworks.	3.12	Agree
4. Social media has decreased my child's confidence and self-esteem.	2.14	Disagree
5. My child remains calm and attentive while using social media platforms.	2.62	Agree
6. My child has been more aggressive since his/her exposure to social media.	2.32	Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.49	Disagree (With Less Impact)
Standard Deviation	.38878	

The over-all computed weighted mean was 2.49 verbally interpreted disagree. This implied that there was **Less Impact** on the effect of daily use of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to mental health.

Excessive use of social media indeed affects one's health like being addicted to smartphones because of the fear of missing out. Social media usage has been correlated with anxiety, loneliness, depression and social isolation (Ostic et al, 2021).

Bizieff (2021) discovered that while social media can have a variety of effects on kids, the bad effects much exceed the good ones. It has been discovered that social media and its long-term effects on children's developing brains have a greater impact.

Table 16: Test of Relationship between Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-aged Children’s Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Sleep

Health Behavior	Pearson r Value	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Nutrition/Diet	0.272	0.028	Reject	Significant
Mental Health	0.673	0.000	Reject	Significant

Table 16 shows the relationship between the impact of social media platforms on school-age children’s lifestyle and health behavior in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of impact to sleep. The computed Pearson r value for health behavior in terms of nutrition was 0.272 with a significant value of 0.028 which was less than the level of significance 0.05. Therefore, the decision was to reject the hypothesis, there was a significant relationship between the impact of social media platforms on the school-age children’s lifestyle and health behavior in terms of impact to sleep. This implied that children’s sleeping habits affected their nutrition/diet since most of their time was spent on social media platforms.

While in terms of impact of sleep and mental health the computed Pearson r value was 0.673 with significant value of 0.000 which was less than the level of significance 0.05. Therefore, the decision hypothesis was rejected. Khare et al. (2021) stated in his study that half of the population of the respondents claimed that they encountered sleep problems during the pandemic and that their screen time using electronic gadgets have also increased, putting them at risk of sleep deprivation and other sleeping problems.

Table 17: Test of Relationship between Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-aged Children’s Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Activity

Health Behavior	Pearson r Value	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Nutrition/Diet	0.108	0.229	Accept	Not Significant
Mental Health	0.410	0.002	Reject	Significant

Table 17 shows the test of relationship between impact of social media platforms on School-age Children's Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan City in terms of Impact to Activity. The computed Pearson r value in terms of nutrition/diet was 0.108 with significant value of 0.229 which was greater than 0.05, therefore there was no significant relationship between the impact of activity and nutrition/diet. The decision was to accept the hypothesis not significant.

This implied that in terms of the impact of activity in social media platforms of children did not affect their nutrition/diet.

While the computed Pearson r value in terms of impact of activity and mental was 0.410 with significant value of 0.002 which was less than the level of significance 0.05, therefore the hypothesis was rejected there was significant relationship between the impact of activity and mental health.

HelpGuide.com (2022) pointed out that social media plays a huge role in one's mental health. Being able to connect with others through social media can ease stress, anxiety, depression, boost self-worth, provide comfort and joy, prevent loneliness, and even add years to one's life. However, on the other hand, everything that is too much can lead to serious risk to one's mental and emotional health. Indicators that social media adversely affects one's health include; spending more time on social media than with real world friends.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study is to identify the Impact of Social Media platforms on School-aged Children's Lifestyle and Health Behavior in selected School in San Juan City, by considering their personal background profiles, lifestyles, involvement in social media, and knowledge in utilizing these platforms. The researchers utilized a questionnaire validated by an expert and utilized it as the main instrument for data collection.

In promoting smart media use, technology can become a beneficial aspect of childhood. Preschoolers can gain the understanding of the alphabet through public television, grade schoolers can utilize educational apps and games, and teenagers can conduct online research on the internet. However, there are some disadvantages to media use as well such as the obesity link, watching violence, sleep & mental health disorders, and exposure to commercials. Children who engage in social media use in their bedrooms frequently have trouble falling asleep at night. Those exposed to cyberbullying through media may develop depression and consider suicide, and those who excessively use media are more likely to be overweight. The inactivity of the children will increase their

likelihood of snacking when glued to screens. They are also exposed to a number of advertisements that promote the intake of commercial foods like potato chips and sugary drinks, which immediately become their snacks of convenience. It has also been recommended that parents encourage children to moderately use smart media by controlling their screen time. (Ben-Joseph, 2022).

The first research question focuses on the profile of the respondent. Most of the guardians/parents of the school-age children who answered the questionnaire were female, which ended up to 38 participants or 76% of the respondents. The sex of school-aged children; respondents were boys, resulting in 39 boys (58%). Age of School-age Children were mostly 6 years old (34%) and in terms of Grade level, 32% of the population came from Grade 1.

Although social media use is demonstrated to be of utility, an excessive or non-correct use may be a risk factor for mental health, including depression, anxiety, and addiction. Excessive use can also increase physical problems due to sedentary lifestyle and may also correlate to inadequate nutrition leading to weight gain, obesity, dental caries and unhealthy eating behavior. Social media can also cause problems with body image and acceptance especially with younger girls with lower self-esteem. Children and adolescents who use social media for several hours a day are also at higher risk of developing behavioral problems, cyberbullying, online grooming, sleep difficulties, eye problems (ex are blurry vision, irritation, burning sensation, conjunctival infection and dry eye disease), headache. Moreover, uncontrolled social media use can also lead to sexting and exposure to pornography, unwanted sexual material online and early sexual activity. The public and medical awareness must rise above this topic. There should be new prevention that must be developed. The Pediatricians should be reminded to have a screening for social media exposure including the amount of time and content, during visits. They can also advise parents on how to steer their children towards suitable content and warn them about the possibility that digital commerce could encourage the consumption of junk food, unhealthy diets and sweetened foods, contributing to obesity and overweight. On the other hand, it is necessary to advise in favor of a good diet, enough exercise, and sleep. Additionally, they want to encourage face-to face interaction and restrict social media use for online conversation. Pediatricians may advise parents to establish guidelines and plans for social media and media device use at home and during the day. (Bozzola et al. 2022)

The second research question highlights the social media platforms involvement. 44 children or 88% of the population owns a gadget. The types of gadgets used by the school-age children to access social media platforms, majority of them used Mobile Phones resulting in 52% of the respondents. In terms of social media accounts, 32 of

them or 64% responded that their children have their own account. In connection, 86% responded that their children did not have their own gadget/s but still had access to any social media platforms. Lastly, YouTube was found to be the most frequently used social media platform among school-aged children, having 43% of the population.

Gagalang (2022) explored the social media use of Filipino learners and its impact on their reading attitudes and competence. He also mentioned that social media use in the Philippines was highly active with an average time of 3 hours and 53 minutes while the country ranked last among the 79 participating countries in reading comprehension in the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). This has led to the discovery that university students' reading skills are negatively impacted by the widespread usage of social media. And although social media platforms do occasionally disseminate information, pique students' interest and analytical capacity, and offer a space for information dissemination and outputs submission, but they typically perform less educational functions.

The third research question features the frequency of the Children's usage of Social Media Platforms on a daily basis in terms of time and hours. The daily frequency usage of social media platforms of the respondents acknowledged that they used these platforms at least 3 to 4 times daily (32%) and around 36% responded that their children used social media in a day for about 1 to 2 hours.

The fourth research question explains the impact of social media platforms in Sleep and Activity of the School-age Children. In terms of Impact to activity, the exposure to social media platforms resulted in having **Less Impact** compared to Impact to Sleep which ended up having **More Impact**.

Rote et al. (2015) conducted a randomized trial to examine the efficacy of walking intervention using social media to increase physical activity. Social media platforms facilitate social networks. The most popular of which is Facebook and can be an effective way to increase physical activity among the users. The final result of the study demonstrated the potential effectiveness of using Facebook to offer a social support group to increase physical activity, specifically in young women. According to them "women in the Facebook Social Support Group increased walking by approximately 1.5 miles/day more than women in the Standard Walking Intervention which, if maintained, could have a profound impact on their future health." Also, users who are friends or a part of the same group can have common grounds/interest which makes it easier to promote such healthy behavior. These physical activities include walking, exercising and running. Summing this up, the use of social media can also be beneficial to several aspects of health (eg, weight loss, healthy eating habits, and reproductive health).

The fifth research question pointed out the effect of social media platforms on the health behavior of school-age children in a selected school in San Juan City in terms of Nutrition/Diet which resulted in **Less Impact** and in Mental Health with **Less Impact** as well.

Utilization of these platforms has escalated in the past few years. Websites and other online tools that facilitate user interactions by allowing users to exchange information, opinions, and interests are referred to as social media. People use these for various reasons such as enjoyment, creating connections, and for further knowledge. Above all, the study found out that adolescent and young adults allocate increased time on online platforms. Moreover, the study mentioned that there are increased concerns with regards to potential adverse effects connected with excessive usage of these platforms especially on cognitive health. Excessive utilization indeed affects one's health like being addicted to smartphones because of the fear of missing out. Social media usage has been correlated with worry, depression and social isolation. (Ostic et al, 2021).

The sixth research question emphasizes the significant relationship between the impact of social media platforms on school-age children's lifestyle and health behavior in a selected school in San Juan City. Tests of the relationship between impact to sleep and nutrition/diet ended up to have a significant relationship. In terms of impact to sleep and mental health also have a significant relationship. Test of relationship between impact to activity and nutrition/diet was brought to not have a significant relationship. Lastly, the impact to activity and mental health was caused to have a significant relationship.

You et al. (2021) reported that the study's findings indicated that a sizable portion of kids utilize social media by the time they are nine years old. Their findings indicate that kids from families with one parent and kids whose moms have little formal schooling spend longer on the internet. Children who had fathers with low levels of education or from low-income backgrounds were more likely to be exposed to social networking sites. It is important for health practitioners to understand how often youngsters access social media. The results of this study provide evidence in favor of the necessity for intervention designers to create strategies for responsible social media use. Future studies in young children are advised to assess their exposure to instant messaging and social networking sites, factors influencing usage, and correlations with relevant health outcomes.

Conclusions

Children in school had experienced several changes as an outcome of the internet. Based on the gathered data. In the questionnaire, many female parents responded. Boys who were six years old and in grade one were more active on social media platforms. Even those without their own gadgets, most school-aged children had access to social media

networks. On the online applications that school-aged children frequent most, YouTube, Tiktok, and Facebook were more prevalent. The respondents stated that their children utilized these platforms for 1- 2 hours every day, at least three to four times per day. Even though the parents acknowledged that their child struggled to sleep after using social media before bedtime, such as Facebook, it did not have an impact on the child's behavior in general. In addition, parents had noticed that even when children were using social media platforms, they still found time to interact with their friends. This showed that even though school-age children used social media platforms, it did not obstruct them from having a fulfilling social life outside of their homes. The parents also confirmed that rules and regulations must be explained in terms of breakfast, lunch, and dinner. In addition, research on children has shown useful applications for social media. The fact that the parents and guardians said that social media had aided their kids in completing their homework and academics suggested that social media might offer some advantages to school-age kids, but excessive usage of the platform could still harm kids' mental health. Despite spending a greater amount of their time on online platforms while eating, the children's use of these platforms had no impact on how they eat. Sometimes kids might feel anxious, worn out, or unhappy, but what they really needed was adequate sleep. School-age children's lifestyles and behaviors were not affected by social media platforms, but appropriate advice and education should still be provided to support the child's optimal overall growth and development and to prevent any dangers that could be harmful to their health.

Recommendations

In particular, with other research studies, there is still need to improve in terms of data, design, and interpretation. To further improve this study, the researchers recommend the future researchers and nursing students;

1. Encourage the parents/ guardians to have a healthy media use like limitation in engaging with social media platforms.
2. Conduct a seminar with parents / guardians educating them about having a family media use plan for their children.
3. Research for other aspects or situations that prolonged exposure in social media could affect one's health.
4. Encourage more students to engage with this kind of studies and elucidate further how too much exposure to social media could alter health.
5. Explore other social media platforms that can influence and further improve one's health, lifestyle, and behavior.
- 6.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the study, ensuring the protection, rights, dignity, and welfare of the respondents were prioritized. A formal permission was submitted to the selected school in San Juan City for approval. The researchers then constructed a 50-item questionnaire checklist entitled “The Impact of Social Media Platforms on School-Aged Children’s Lifestyle and Health Behavior in a Selected School in San Juan”, and had it validated by experts. Upon distribution, all of the participants were informed of the purpose, expectations and research methodology, and they will be asked to sign consent forms explaining that the survey is strictly confidential and voluntary. The questionnaires will be disseminated via Google Forms. The data gathered will then be collected, tallied and tabulated. Confidentiality and Right to Decline were proposed to all the respondents; they were informed that all personal information gathered will be used only for the purpose of acquiring details useful for the research.

Moreover, by participating in our nursing research as a respondent, any information given to us will be used for the purposes of nursing research and any other healthcare related things.

The personal data provided relating to the child will be retained by the researchers for the purposes of school related activities and be able to provide such interventions relating to this kind of problem. This may also require the personal data as well as your child’s data including relevant details in their daily lives to be shared with the researchers. The researchers assured its respondents that confidential information would not be discussed to anyone unless they authorize the researchers to do so.

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